

Accurate Switching Energy Measurement of Wide Band-Gap Semiconductors at Low Current

Gustavo S. Zappulla^{1,2}, Bernardo Cougo¹, Marco Vinício T. Andrade^{1,2}, Lenin M. F. Morais³

¹ IRT Saint-Exupéry, France

² Graduate Program in Electrical Engineering, Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG), Brazil

³ Department of Electronic Engineering, Federal University of Minas (UFMG), Brazil

Corresponding author: Gustavo S. Zappulla, gustavo.sathler@irt-saintexupery.com

Abstract

Several applications require efficiency-oriented design, in which high performance wide bandgap semiconductors are used in low power converters. Precise switching loss estimation at low current is essential to achieve accurate design, although it is not frequently addressed in the literature. This paper reviews dynamic characterization methods with focus on wide bandgap technologies. The Double Pulse and Modified Opposition methods are compared in order to highlight advantages and limitations of each one, especially at low current. Both are verified through simulations and in a real test bench, whose results are compared with datasheet curves and evaluated through a case study.

1 Introduction

Loss estimation is a crucial step for the design of switch mode power converters (SMPC) because it determines the rated efficiency of the system and the required cooling solution. This is particularly important in the context of converter optimization [1], [2], in which several criteria to achieve an optimal solution require a valid and precise model to represent the system.

An important improvement in the performance of converters has been achieved with the use of wide band-gap (WBG) thanks to its better figures of merit (FOM) compared to silicon-based (Si) ones [3]. For a same on-state resistance ($R_{DS(on)}$) level, WBG devices have an input capacitance several times smaller than Si ones, leading to faster transitions and, consequently, lower switching losses. At the same time, it allows higher switching frequencies that contributes for the reduction of passive dimensions, leading to a higher power density.

In the context of efficiency-oriented design, devices may be used in current ranges considerably smaller than their capabilities, in order to reduce as much as possible their power losses. However, it is uncommon that manufacturers' datasheets provide switching energy curves in a range below 10%-20%

of the device's nominal current. In most cases, designers should estimate switching energies, calculate them by some analytical model or even perform dynamic characterization.

Some works have proposed analytical switching loss models based on datasheet parameters [4], [5]. However, most of them do not consider all the phenomena involved on the switching at low currents. In particular, switching energies at low current are dominated by the charge and discharge of the device's output capacitance (C_{oss}) [6].

The energy stored in C_{oss} is provided in device's datasheet (E_{oss}), which is calculated by the non-linear characteristic of C_{oss} as a function of the drain voltage (v_{ds}) by the equation

$$E_{oss} = \int_0^{V_{DD}} v_{ds} \cdot C_{oss}(v_{ds}) dv_{ds} \quad (1)$$

for a dc bus voltage V_{DD} . Reference [7] provides good explanation about the charging process of C_{oss} , which causes energy loss E_{qoss} in the equivalent series resistance calculated by

$$E_{qoss} = \int_0^{V_{DD}} (V_{DD} - v_{ds}) \cdot C_{oss}(v_{ds}) dv_{ds} \quad (2)$$

For the typical profile of the output capacitance in semiconductors, as shown in Fig. 1, E_{qoss} is always higher than E_{oss} and shall be taken into account

Fig. 1: Output capacitance C_{oss} obtained from device's C3M0040120J1 (Wolfspeed) datasheet. The energies E_{oss} , E_{qoss} and $E_{oss} + E_{qoss}$ were analytically calculated as a function of V_{DS} .

for an accurate losses estimation. The parasitic capacitances in parallel with C_{oss} shall also be considered in the calculations. A brief review about switching behavior is provided in Section 2.

Furthermore, the dynamic characterization test commonly accepted by manufacturers for measuring switching energies - the Double Pulse Test (DPT) - has a shortcoming related to the stored energy in (C_{oss}) [7], which provides inaccurate results at low currents.

Understanding the characterization methods enables the designer to better evaluate the data provided by the manufacturers and to propose a more precise loss estimation according to the targeted application. This topic will be addressed with further details in Section 3, together with a review of the Modified Opposition Method (MOM).

The two methods are compared through Spice simulations (Section 4) and experimentally (Section 5). An overall discussion of the results are provided in Section 6. Section 7 presents a case study, followed by the conclusions.

2 Semiconductor Transitions

The behavior of switches at turn-on and turn-off transitions are presented in Fig. 2. This analysis assumes a device with third-quadrant operation as Si/SiC MOSFETs and GaN HEMTs. The words "body diode" and "channel" are used for the sake of generality, even if GaN devices do not present these properties.

When switch Q_1 is closed, the current i_L flows through its channel (i_{ch}) and C_{oss1} (equivalent to device's $C_{ds} + C_{gd}$) is discharged. Capacitor C_{oss2} stores the energy E_{oss} . Once Q_1 is driven to turn-

Fig. 2: Diagram and waveforms of (a) Q_1 's hard turn-off, Q_2 's ZVS turn-on; (b) Q_1 's hard turn-on, Q_2 's ZVS turn-off.

off state, part of i_L starts to flow through C_{oss1} and C_{oss2} [4], charging the first one and discharging the second one. The energy stored in C_{oss2} is gradually transferred to the inductor, while C_{oss1} absorbs the same amount of energy E_{oss} from the source.

At the end of this process, the remaining current on the channel of Q_1 is extinguished. Current i_L keeps flowing through the capacitors until the voltage on C_{oss2} become slightly negative, which provokes the conduction of Q_2 's body diode. After the deadtime, Q_2 is driven on.

The crossover between i_{ch} and v_{ds} constitutes the transition in device's linear region, which produces losses on the device Q_1 ("hard-switching"), but the charge and discharge of the devices' output capacitors are considered lossless. Any relevant crossover occurs on the bottom device, because the device's turn-on occurs at a negligible V_{ds} or "zero-voltage switching" (ZVS).

When Q_2 is driven off, as long the current in the device is negative (flowing from the source to the drain), its voltage v_{ds} is clamped by its body diode. In this situation, a ZVS turn-on occurs, causing negligible losses on Q_2 . It is important to mention that, to ensure Q_2 's ZVS, the deadtime shall be enough to ensure the complete process of C_{oss1} charging and C_{oss2} discharging. Otherwise, Q_2 is driven on with a non-negligible v_{ds} voltage, causing a partial hard-switching. Further details about ZVS conditions can be found in [8].

After deadtime, Q_1 is driven and current i_L is gradually transferred from Q_2 's body diode to Q_1 's channel. A voltage drop on Q_1 's v_{ds} is observed due to the parasitic inductance in the path, which generates an opposite voltage on the switch to counteract the positive di/dt on Q_1 .

Once the body diode's current reaches zero, bottom device's v_{ds} is no more clamped and Q_1 's channel is conducting. At this moment, capacitor C_{oss1} discharges its entire energy (E_{oss}) on Q_1 's channel. At the same time, C_{oss2} is charged by the bus, whose charging current circulates through Q_1 's channel, causing the energy dissipation E_{qoss} defined by Eq. 2. A current peak can be observed in Q_1 due to E_{qoss} , which also includes the body diode reverse recovery current in the case of Si/SiC MOSFETs. Since the discharge of C_{oss1} is an internal phenomenon, it cannot be seen in the device's current measurement.

In summary, at least three energies are dissipated during this (hard) turn-on transition: E_{oss} stored on C_{oss1} ; E_{qoss} for charging C_{oss2} ; and the term related to the crossover between i_{ds} and v_{ds} . At zero current, this last term is zero, and the minimum energy at device's turn-on is defined by the sum $E_{oss} + E_{qoss}$.

3 Dynamic characterization methods

3.1 Double pulse test

The double pulse test (DPT) is the most used approach to measure switching energies [9]. It consists in measuring the switch voltage v_{DS} and current i_{DS} waveforms simultaneously and obtain the energy increase over the transitions. Reference [9] proposes a detailed analysis, including the most relevant factors that could impact the consistency of measurement.

The circuit typically used for implementing this test is shown in Fig. 3. By applying a first pulse in the gate of the device under tests (DUT), the inductor's current increases. The DUT is driven off at the rated current, during which the inductor current flows through the free-wheeling device with negligible variation. Then, the DUT is driven on with approximately same current. Current and voltage waveforms at the rated current are multiplied and integrated, in order to obtain the switching energies. An important advantage is the fact that measure-

Fig. 3: Typical circuit diagram of DPT.

ments of switching energies are performed with negligible variation in junction temperature, which allows device's characterization under different and specific temperatures.

However, since the energies are measured during transition time intervals, the energy E_{oss} to charge C_{oss} is seen as a parcel of loss dissipated during turn-off, and not at turn-on. This shortcoming impact mainly the losses estimation of ZVS topologies, producing an overestimation per device proportional to the switching frequency.

In addition, the real implementation of DPT for WBG devices presents some major concerns due to the fast transitions. The main difficulties are related to [9]: 1) the bandwidth of sensors; 2) the sensibility of the results to the time misalignment between voltage and current; and 3) grounding loop effects, which are also intensified by the probes.

Finally, the DPT increase the parasitic inductance of the system, because it is necessary to insert a current probe in series with the power loop. For recent power modules with integrated decoupling capacitors, the measurement by DPT is not possible in the real configuration, since the current i_{DS} becomes inaccessible.

3.2 Modified Opposition Method

The Modified Opposition Method was proposed in [10] as a non-intrusive method for dynamic characterization of semiconductors. It consists in an indirect measurement, in which four similar devices are tested in two full-bridges through a test bench with accurately characterized elements. The diagram of the circuit is shown in Fig. 4.

The test is performed in two parts. First, a test with a trapezoidal current, which is implemented through

Fig. 4: Typical circuit diagram and waveforms of the Modified Opposition Method.

a ZVS modulation, resulting in four devices switching at approximately the same current level with negligible turn-on losses. In this test, the amplitude of the trapezoidal current is tuned by the phase-shift between the two legs, and E_{off} energies can be measured under different current levels.

Below a given current limit $i_{L(limZVS)}$, partial ZVS occurs, because the time required to perform the voltage transition is inferior to the deadtime. Although this term is measured as a turn-off energy, actually it occurs in the complementary device after the deadtime during its turn-on. The value of $i_{L(limZVS)}$ is inversely proportional to the deadtime.

The second test is performed with a dc current, in which the two switching legs are controlled with zero phase shift and with adjustable duty cycles, allowing to set a dc current in the inductor. The resulting current waveform has a dc profile with a negligible ripple. The results present losses caused by turn-on and turn-off transitions (hard-switching). Turn-on energies are therefore segregated from turn-off ones measured in the trapezoidal test.

In both tests, losses caused by switching energies are obtained by measuring the total input power of the system and compensating the losses not related to the devices switching. These terms include losses on passives, pcb paths and the conduction losses of the devices themselves. For this reason, this method is susceptible to measurement errors due to the difficulty to take into account all the phenomena that produce energy losses in the test bench. An improvement with more precise guide-

lines for a proper losses compensation is provided in [11].

In contrast to DPT, the MOM measures the losses already considering the correct assignment of the term E_{oss} on E_{on} energies instead of E_{off} . It also includes the energy E_{dt} , dissipated during the body diode conduction during the deadtime, not negligible in WBG devices. This term can be included as a switching energy, once it is proportional to the switching frequency.

Finally, the MOM requires a longer time to be performed due to current stabilization and dc measurements, differently from the DPT that is performed in few microseconds. Consequently, the DUTs and the test bench are subject to temperature variation, which in turn changes the performance of many elements, including the own on-state resistance of the switches under test. For that reason, the test bench and the DUTs losses have to be compensated as a function of their temperatures.

4 Simulation results

The DPT and MOM were performed by simulations at same conditions through the software LTSpice with the model of the SiC device C3M0040120J1 (Wolfspeed). The Spice diagram of the DPT is shown in Fig. 5. The simulation of MOM considers two identical legs as the one used in the DPT, but without the impedance of a current-viewer resistor (CVR), represented in the diagram by the elements L_3 , L_6 and R_2 .

For the DPT, two scenarios were simulated: one considering the impedance of the CVR SDN-414-01, which has $10.17m\Omega$ and $6nH$; another without this impedance, supposing an ideal current measurement.

Some parasitic elements were included in the power and driver loops in order to reproduce more accurately a real test bench, similar for both tests, which includes a $67pF$ capacitance in parallel with the main inductor and $18pF$ in parallel with the switches (values taken from a real test bench used in some experiments). Junction temperatures was kept in $25^\circ C$. Results are shown in Figs. 6 and 7.

Turn-off analysis

Comparing DPT turn-off curves (Fig. 6), the energy measured by DPT with CVR and DPT without CVR are quite similar, presenting a difference at maximum current (60A) about $2.0\mu J$ (DPT with CVR

Fig. 5: Spice diagram schematics implemented for the DPT, including CVR impedance.

Fig. 6: Turn-off energies obtained by simulations through DPT with CVR impedance, MOM and DPT without CVR impedance.

2.2% higher). This small discrepancy is caused by the fact that the effective V_{DS} during the channel crossover is higher due to the increased overshoot, as a consequence of higher parasitic inductance.

Concerning the differences between the results of both methods, MOM turn-off energy is around $1.6\mu\text{J}$ at 7A, in contrast to DPT (without CVR) that results in $29\mu\text{J}$ at the same current, $27.4\mu\text{J}$ higher than MOM. This value is close to the calculated E_{oss} at 600V ($26.2\mu\text{J}$), in which the energy of the parallel capacitance (18pF , $3.2\mu\text{J}$) is included. At 60A, the difference between both is $11.7\mu\text{J}$. By subtracting $27.4\mu\text{J}$ from DPT without CVR to compensate E_{oss} , the deviation becomes $39.1\mu\text{J}$, which corresponds to the energy E_{dt} .

Turn-on analysis

At turn-on (Fig. 7), DPT with CVR presents an energy $4.8\mu\text{J}$ lower than DPT without CVR at zero current (7.7%). This occurs because part of the energy E_{qoss} is dissipated on the CVR resistance. At 60A, DPT with CVR is $29.6\mu\text{J}$ lower than DPT

Fig. 7: Turn-on energies obtained by simulations through DPT with CVR impedance, MOM and DPT without CVR impedance.

without CVR. As previously explained, the voltage drop on parasitic inductances (that counteract the positive di_{DS}/dt at turn-on) brings a reduced effective V_{DS} during the channel crossover, resulting in lower energies.

Comparing the two methods, DPT without CVR is $27.4\mu\text{J}$ lower than MOM, and this value matches the difference due to E_{oss} , similarly verified in E_{off} measurement. At 60A, the difference increases to $64.5\mu\text{J}$. By adding $27.4\mu\text{J}$ in the DPT without CVR curve, the deviation is close to the energy E_{dt} ($37.1\mu\text{J}$).

Both methods have the expected energies at zero current: DPT without CVR presents $62.1\mu\text{J}$; MOM presents $89.6\mu\text{J}$. These values are similar to the calculated energies of, respectively, E_{qoss} ($53.4\mu\text{J}$) and $E_{oss} + E_{qoss}$ ($79.6\mu\text{J}$), in which the energy of probes and inductor parasitic capacitances shall be considered.

5 Experimental Results

Both characterization methods were implemented in the test bench depicted in Fig. 8 with the device C3M0040120J1. The test bench circuit has two half-bridges, in which both were used for the MOM and only one for the DPT. The sensor used on both tests are identified in Table 1. MOM was performed at 200kHz switching frequency.

Following conditions were considered for both tests: $V_{DD} = 600\text{V}$; $R_{Geat} = 2.5\Omega$; $V_{GS} = -4\text{V(off)}/+15\text{V(on)}$. The gate drivers used has 11A peak capability, which is enough to properly drive the devices.

Figures 9 and 10 present the resulting energies obtained through experimental verification of the MOM and DPT, together with the energy curves

Fig. 8: Test bench used for implementing DPT and MOM. A CVR was included for DPT.

Tab. 1: Probes and sensors used in the experiment.

		Type	Sensor
DPT	Voltage	Probe TTIVP1 Tektronix 1kV 1GHz	
	Current	CVR SDN-414-01 T&M 10.17mΩ 400MHz	
MOM	Voltage	Multimeter Keysight 34461A	
	Current	Multimeter Keysight 34461A Probe 3274 Hioki 150A 10MHz	

provided in device's datasheet, which is also measured through DPT by the manufacturer. Devices' junction temperatures for the MOM were estimated by measuring the case temperature using a thermal camera and evaluated using the datasheet value of junction-to-case thermal resistance (R_{th-jc}).

Turn-off analysis

Concerning Fig. 9, as verified by simulations, at the lowest current (9A) the datasheet turn-off energy at 9A is $28.9\mu\text{J}$, compared to $4.2\mu\text{J}$ for MOM (datasheet is $24.7\mu\text{J}$ higher). This difference is close to E_{oss} analytically calculated ($26.2\mu\text{J}$), taking into account that MOM also includes E_{dt} at 9A. As the current increases, curves become closer to each other, until a current level of 30A, in which they have approximately the same value. At this point, the energy E_{dt} included in MOM compensates the energy E_{oss} included in datasheet curve.

To provide an estimation of E_{dt} , some values are calculated (based on datasheet information), considering that the body diode are in conduction during the entire deadtime (100ns): $3.7\mu\text{J}$ at 9A; $10.0\mu\text{J}$ at 20A; $16.7\mu\text{J}$ at 30A. Therefore, assuming the analytically calculated value for E_{oss} ($26.2\mu\text{J}$), the deviation between datasheet and MOM becomes bigger than the expected E_{dt} as the current increases.

Fig. 9: Turn-off energies experimentally obtained through DPT with CVR impedance, MOM and DPT without CVR impedance.

Fig. 10: Turn-on energies experimentally obtained through DPT with CVR impedance, MOM and DPT without CVR impedance.

Finally, results of DPT for turn-off energies were not conclusive, since the curve presents a not expected profile. In order to investigate this issue, Fig. 11 presents a comparison between current waveforms obtained by DPT simulations and the experiment. It was observed a residual current after a turn-off transition at 7A, that is not included into the integration limits.

This phenomenon is assumed to be caused by ground loop effects and other parasitics coupled in the test bench, but its origin requires further investigation. The abnormal profile obtained through DPT suggests a poor current measurement, which puts in evidence the challenges of properly performing the DPT with high speed switches.

Turn-on analysis

For turn-on energies, the results obtained through DPT have a profile coherent with datasheet ones. As verified in the simulations, these energies are more impacted by the parasitics of the test bench, which can explain the different slopes and zero current losses between DPT and datasheet (this one was linearly extrapolated, giving a value around $92.0\mu\text{J}$). For this reason, MOM is compared exclu-

Fig. 11: Comparison of current waveforms verified by simulations (red) and experimentally (blue) at 0A (turn-on) and 7A (turn-off).

sively with DPT.

At 0A, turn-on energies measured through MOM and DPT are respectively $88.8\mu\text{J}$ and $60.2\mu\text{J}$. By subtracting the energies of the parasitic capacitances, estimated $7.8\mu\text{J}$ for MOM and $13.9\mu\text{J}$ for DPT, it leads to respectively $80.1\mu\text{J}$ and $46.3\mu\text{J}$. These values are consistent with the expected E_{qoss} and $E_{oss} + E_{qoss}$, ($79.6\mu\text{J}$ and $53.4\mu\text{J}$ respectively). The divergence between calculated and experimental was more accentuated for DPT (13.3%), which is supposed to occur due to the integration limits of DPT that underestimates the energies.

At 29A, MOM is $61.2\mu\text{J}$ higher than DPT. Subtracting the $28.6\mu\text{J}$ of difference at 0A, the net deviation at 29A becomes $32.6\mu\text{J}$, which is considerably higher than the maximum E_{dt} ($16.0\mu\text{J}$). This discrepancy can be explained by the junction temperature increase, that causes higher turn-on energies.

6 Discussion of results

The discussion about the results evaluated through the simulations and the experiment of the characterization methods are summarized below:

- 1) The underestimation of E_{on} and overestimation of E_{off} caused by E_{oss} stored on DUT's C_{oss} have been identified and validated through the simulations. Correct measurement of these energies is made by MOM. In the same way, MOM measures higher switching energies than DPT because it considers the parcel of energy due to the body diode conduction during the deadtime.
- 2) The inductance added by the current sensor at DPT had a relevant impact on the results: it increases turn-off energies, since it stores an amount of energy that is completely discharged on the

Fig. 12: Simplified DAB topology diagram.

switching channel; it decreases turn-on energies because the high di/dt on i_{ds} provokes a voltage drop on the parasitic inductance that reduces the effective voltage v_{ds} during the transition.

3) In low currents, turn-off energies measured by DPT are several times higher than those measured by MOM (at 9A the ratio is 6.8 times). In ZVS topologies, this discrepancies may provoke considerable estimation errors.

7 Case study

In the frame of a converter design for aircraft applications, the ZVS topology Dual-Active Bridge (DAB) has been evaluated. Its circuit diagram is provided in Fig. 12, together with a typical input waveforms. For this case study, it was considered a converter with nominal output power (P_{out}) of 5000W and input voltage (V_{in}) of 600Vdc. Other parameters are omitted in this analysis. The SiC MOSFET C3M0040120J1 was considered among the devices evaluated. For the sake of simplicity, only the losses on the primary legs are analyzed.

Referring to Fig. 9, E_{off} curve from the datasheet suggests a convergence towards $26.2\mu\text{J}$ and this value has been assumed to be the same in the range of 0A to 9A. Figure 13 presented the estimated total losses on the primary side full-bridge devices, at 100kHz and 300kHz, through datasheet curves and MOM.

The results show that, at 100kHz and nominal power (5000W), estimation losses by datasheet curves are 72% higher than losses by MOM (26.2W versus 15.3W). At 300kHz, this overestimation increases to 151% (54.5W versus 21.7).

In conclusion, this case study illustrates the discrepancies that may occur in a preliminary converter losses estimation. For high efficiency and high power density converters, switching energies should be carefully considered, taking into account predominant phenomena at low currents and the dynamic characterization method used.

Fig. 13: Estimated total losses on primary side full-bridge devices, using datasheet curves and MOM characterization results. Evaluated at 100kHz and 300kHz.

8 Conclusions

This paper aimed to provide an analysis of semiconductor switching energies at low currents towards accurate measurements, which is essential for precise losses estimation. Because switching losses of wide bandgap devices are dominated by its parasitic output capacitance, measures obtained through the Double Pulse Test (DPT) present relevant deviations from the effective dissipated energy in each transition, which could be verified when compared to the Modified Opposition Method (MOM).

Differently from previous contributions, the dynamic characterization methods have been compared through simulations and experiments at same conditions. A case study of a ZVS topology showed that losses have been overestimated when based on curves provided by manufacturers' datasheets. The results demonstrate that estimation errors become considerably relevant at switching frequency levels currently used in wide bandgap devices.

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